

Information Need and Seeking Behaviour of Students in Royal Institute of Management and Advanced Studies, M.P.

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Abstract:- This study examines the needs for knowledge and the behaviour of graduate students. Behavioural research plays an important role in improving library collections, increasing access to information and improving services to meet users' information needs. It is important because of the role they will play in establishing resource-user relationships. They seek information. Most respondents do not use electronic information resources (e.g., books, magazines, the internet, and personal collections) as great resources. Use the data collection method to use the questionnaire method to assess student behaviour. Conclusions.

Keywords:- Graduate Student, Information, Information Seeking Behaviour, Information Need, College Library.

I. INTRODUCTION

Information is power. It is an essential source of human life on earth. Information is an important source that is considered an essential part of everyone's existence. Knowledge is a basic necessity of life that helps meet other needs such as food and shelter. Information is just as important to any library as it is to its users. According to Bell, "Knowledge is related to news, facts, statistics, reports, actions, taxpayers, judicial decisions, decisions, and so on." The process of acquiring, using, and using information. It is known as information-seeking behaviour. The behaviour of the search for information is primarily about what kind of information is needed for what reasons and how the information is obtained, tested and used. Ellis (1989), in his model of behaviour-seeking behaviour, identified six actions in the search for information, namely: first, binding, browsing, separating, monitoring, and deleting. Users feel that the library cannot meet their needs, and they spend time searching for information and finding needs based on those needs. In keeping with this consideration, current research has been conducted to evaluate the behaviour of information seekers in order to meet the needs of users.

➤ *The library system at RIMAS*

The library is the soul of RIMAS academics. It is designed to meet the information needs of users for the purpose of providing access to information "anytime, anywhere." RIMAS is located in the district of Madhya Pradesh. It was founded in 1996. The has a well-stocked central library of textbooks and reference books for various subjects like B.pharma, D.pharma, MBA, D.Ed, B.ED, BCA.

There are subscriptions for printed journals, electronic journals, and e-books.

➤ *Information Center*

Part of the library, the information centre is equipped with computer nodes that have internet access. It has an excellent collection of CDs and DVDs on science and technology to promote audio and visual reading for students. E-Information Center

It is part of a central library and consists of computers, printers, scanners, CD/DVD writers, e-database and journal access, and a server comprising a digital library. The content here is collected from a variety of sources and is stored in an organised format. Students can find and conduct their own research studies.

➤ *Xerox and other resources*

A separate Xerox machine is available for students and teachers in the library.

II. A BOOK REVIEW

A literature review plays a very important role in the research process. The purpose of the literature review is to provide relevant information to the researcher. Literature research shows that the books published in this area are numerous. Some of them are as follows:

Shaukin and Kushik (2002) report on a study of sociologists who find ethical information at Haryana universities. Studies have shown that most social workers visit the library daily. A popular search tool was to identify and summarise journals and quotes into articles. popular sources of information for current magazines and books.

Williamson & Watson (2007) The information acquisition process involves a number of basic steps, such as identifying information, selecting sources, considering information needs, and determining information acquisition strategies and evaluating selected strategies. Dhyani (1974) conducted a survey of 100 students at the Rajasthan Library, Jaipur. Research has shown that students have shown an interest in using the library at a level.

Shokeen and Kushik (2002) Behavioral learning for students seeking knowledge at Haryana Studies have shown that most of them visit the library every day.

In 2013, Singh and Dheeraj Kumar conducted a study to assess access to information and use of it by the faculty of Guru Angad Dev Veterinary and Animal Sciences (GADVASU). Data was collected from faculty with a response rate of 62% using an online questionnaire. User targets, location for information, preferences compared to online resources, information access issues, etc. have been examined. The results show that internet access to information resources has affected users' access to the library. Two similar studies by Keshav and Savanur and Singh and Satija sought to understand the behaviour of agricultural scientists and showed that in both cases, users were satisfied with the library's services and relied heavily on the library collection. The findings also indicate that the guidance and use of library resources is required to assist the user in meeting some of his or her information needs.

Raveen Kumar (2013) reviewed to identify the inquisitive behaviour of members of the BPS Women's faculty in Khanpur. The study was based on a questionnaire approach. Key findings of the survey reveal useful facts about the research that faculty members use Google to find information. Most experts say that information is not available online. Their research shows that the majority of intelligence members sought information on speech preparation, information retention, and research work. Clever members use a variety of methods to obtain information. Ramesh (2012) A study conducted by members of the ICFAI Business School Hyderabad's intelligence to analyse information needs and queries for library resources A well-structured questionnaire was developed in this study, in which the data of 70 faculty members was collected and analyzed. The key findings of the survey revealed useful facts about the fact that library experts need to help them make good use of library resources wisely and intelligently. Make members aware of access to the library resources available to them.

Poornima and Vikas (2005) conducted a study on the knowledge needs of skills in Manipur. Research shows that with the exception of a few s or universities, many schools do not have access to IT (lack of library resources). He studied the skills requirements of and university students. Learn how to use computers, online journals, and digital resources.

Kumar K and Tholkappian (2013) conducted a research study on the behaviour of library users at women's educational institutions in the Vellore region. Tamil Nadu has indicated that the effectiveness of any library depends largely on the selection of the library collection. The findings revealed that the library is widely used by users to study in the library.

Sarkhel and Khan (2014) cite studies to gain insight into the ethics and use of the library by faculty members of an

agricultural in Bangladesh. The purpose of the research was to determine the need and purpose of their knowledge of the library services available to them in the library. The study collected data on the information needs of intelligence members. Data was collected from 600 members out of 905 members through an open and closed questionnaire.

Natarajan (2012) describes the various types of electrical appliances. The e-environment discusses the behaviour of students, researchers, and teachers seeking information. Explain more about the role of library staff in providing electronic resources to different user communities.

➤ *Purposes*

- 1) Evaluate students' knowledge and behavioural needs.
- 2) Determine the obstacles that students face in gaining access to information.
- 3) Understand why you're looking for information.
- 4) Assessing students' awareness and use of library resources.
- 5) Identify the different types of sources that students use.

➤ *How to do it*

How to Put This Knowledge into Practice The RIMAS test methodology was adopted to collect data from Bogardis' ability members, and it states that "the questionnaire is an open list of questions that different people are encouraged to answer." Questionnaire tools can be cheaper and faster than personal interviews. Hooligan and Hott, in the definition of the word "questionnaire," usually the name of the question, refer to finding the answers to the question. A questionnaire was conducted to gather information about library use, online resources, and the purpose of the library. A total of 200 questions were randomly distributed to respondents in libraries and classrooms, as well as open and closed questions seeking information on student behavior. Of the 200, 200 completed questions were returned to users, with a total response rate of 100%. Data obtained from responses was analyzed, categorized, and tabulated to understand the student's seeking information and knowledge needs using mathematical methods. Data analysis and presentation.

The data collected was analyzed using calculations and percentages and presented in the form of a table (descriptive statistics) as researchers approached students by sorting out all the skills individually.

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	120	60%
Female	80	40%
Total	200	100%

Fig 1: Distribution of respondents by gender

Table 1 shows that 60% of respondents are male and only 40% are female.

Table 2: Distribution of respondents according to reading level

Level of Learning	Frequency	Percentage
100 Level (first year)	80	40%
200 Level (second year)	70	35%
300 Level (third year)	30	15%
400 Level (fourth year)	20	10%
Total	200	100%

Fig -2 Distribution of respondents according to reading level

Table 2 indicates the distribution of graduate students according to their academic year. The majority of students were 100 and 40%, 200 and 35%, and 300 out of 15% and 400 graduates. It was because 400-level students were no longer in their studies due to the deadline to meet and present the project for the final year.

Table 3: Frequency of Library use by respondents

Use of the Library	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	110	55%
Every month	10	5%
Twice a week	30	15%
Once a week	30	15%
It's rare	20	10%
Total	200	100%

Fig -3 Frequency of Library use by respondents

From Table 3 above, it is concluded that 55% visit the library regularly, 5% monthly, 15% twice a week, 15% once a week, and 10% rarely.

Table 4: Purpose of the Inquisition

Purpose	Frequency	Percentage
Entertainment	-	-
Personal Development	10	5%
Research	10	5%
Test and course Work	40	20%
Assignments	140	70%
Total	200	100%

Fig - 4 Purpose of the Search

Table 4 shows that with 70% of RIMAS graduates placing first-class assignments, research information is ranked second, and 5% of respondents report doing research. indicated, with 5% doing self-improvement and 20% doing experiments and courses. The purpose of the search for information was very low, as no student indicated entertainment as the purpose of the search for information. It was concluded that the main need for knowledge of graduates was knowledge of class assignments.

Table 5 shows that personal collections, library textbooks and magazines, and online libraries are the most preferred ways to search for information by graduate students at Rimas at 45%, 15%, and 25%, respectively. The RIMAS online website and other sources are the preferred ways to search for information.

Table 5: How to search for MDS undergraduate information

How to search Information	Frequency	Percentage
Personal Collection	90	45%
MDS Online Database	20	10%
Library Textbook and journal	30	15%
Library (Online)	50	25%
Other Sources	10	5%
Total	200	100%

Table 6: Information resource for selected students for consultation

Preferred Information Service	Frequency	Percentage
Class Notes	70	35%
Internet	60	30%
A textbook	40	20%
E books and journals	20	10%
Reference	10	5%

Fig - 5 How to search for MDS undergraduate information

Fig - 6 Information materials for selected students for consultation

It is indicated in Table 6 above that the speech notes are the preferred source of information to consult with the 35% of respondents who indicate this. The second most popular source of information is the Internet, with 60% of respondents indicating a textbook, followed by 40% of respondents. The most preferred sources for consulting are e-books, e-journals, and reference materials. The Internet, lectures, and textbooks are the most popular sources, while reference materials, newspapers, and e-magazines are the least used.

Table 7: Use of Electronic Website

Yes	65%
No	35%
Total	100%

Fig -7 Use of Electronic Database

It is evident from Table 7 that the library registers electronic learning materials to meet the information needs of students. Students at Rimas were asked to sign up for electronic educational material to meet their knowledge needs, whether they use it or not. 65% said they use an electronic database, and 35% do not use an electronic database.

Table 8: Problems / Challenges encountered during the Search for Information

Problems/Challenges	frequency	Percentage
Network Failure/Flexibility	130	65%
Insufficient information on use of electronic resource/OPAC	60	30%
Insufficient librarians Library The disobedient attitude of Library staff	10	5%
Total	200	100%

Fig -8 Problems / Challenges Facing the Search for Information

Table 8 shows that the main problem for respondents while searching for information is network failure or flexibility, with 65% of respondents showing the same. This is followed by insufficient information regarding power utilisation/OPAC and dispersed information from various sources by 30% and 5%, respectively.

Table 9: E Utility Frequency E

E-Resources	frequency	Percentage
CD-Rom Database	70	35%
E- Journal	50	25%
E- Books	42	21%
An online Database	38	19%
TOTAL	200	100%

Fig -9 Frequency of Use of E Resources

Table 9 shows that the CD-ROM website is widely used by 35% of electronic resources, 25% of journals, 21% of books, and 19% of online sites.

Table 10: Troubleshooting strategies

Strategies/suggestions	Frequency	Percentage
The student should be trained to use it OPAC and an electronic website	70	35
Development of Internet networks	110	55%
Qualified professionals should be employed	---	---
Information items should be good it is organized and protected	20	10%
Library staff should change method of operation	--	--
Total	200	100%

Fig 10: Troubleshooting strategies and suggestions

From Table 10 above, Mandasaur students have been asked to make suggestions on the list to improve their access to information. 55% suggested improvements to online networks, while 35% suggested that they should be trained in OPAC and the use of power resources. Although 20% of the suggested information content should be consistent and protected, No guidance was given to hire qualified professionals and library staff to change their practice. Search chat.

The study concluded that the majority of respondents were men. The majority of students regularly visit the library, and the smallest part do not use the library or have their own collection of books. It is well known that Rimas students need knowledge related to academic activities such as assignments, research, assessment, and academic work as well as personal development. This is important information for students who need knowledge of class assignments. It was also revealed that the selected information resources for consulting students for RIMAS are lectures, online information, textbooks, and the internet, which is widely used in the educational library. The reason for the low use of e-journals and e-books may not be related to students'

inadequate knowledge of the use of electronic information according to the direct response found in search engines and shown in Table 6. This is linked to Table 7 where the findings indicate that RIMAS student usage is low. The electronic section of the library saw that most students use the Google search engine. The biggest challenges RIMAS students face in satisfying their curiosity are not having enough information about internet network failures and fluctuations and the use of electronic devices. Students should be trained in the use of OPAC and electronic information systems, and information content should be well organised and protected.

III. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The information needs of RIMAS students vary, but depend largely on the connection of the library, their personal collections, study notes, library textbooks, and articles. The study concluded that RIMAS students are dissatisfied with the internet connection and have limited knowledge of the use of electronic devices while trying to obtain the desired information.

The following suggestions and recommendations are made based on the current research and the suggestions given to respondents.

- The library should improve the maintenance of an adequate collection of information about the needs of the RIMAS library.
- Training courses should be organized regularly to raise awareness about the availability of electronic resources in the library.
- Computers and networks should be improved in the operation of the ICT library.

IT staff at RIMAS should be tasked with solving ongoing problems related to the Internet, hardware, and software.

- There is a need for a rich collection of printed and electronic magazines at the national and international level.
- Employees should be given the task of resolving ongoing problems in order to reduce the theft of library materials.

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